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Proposal Summary

Many research articles conclude by saying, “this methodology may be used in other systems”. The articles may be published in open access journals along with data and code, but does that equate to open-source *science*? Open-source science is transparent, accessible, reproducible, and inclusive. For any given article, how long would it take not only to reproduce the results but to use that knowledge to make new discoveries? The reader must fully understand the science and methodology, acquire the data, run the code, and complete the analysis.

In an undergraduate lab, students analyze a scientific topic then make calculations. The science is explained clearly, and computational tasks are simplified by using small, prepared datasets and a limited but fundamental set of coding techniques. If a researcher can present the science behind their article in the context of a marine sciences lab, then the science is *accessible*.

The lab used a small, prepared dataset, but the original data is required to reproduce the article. Getting satellite data can be a challenge, and the process used to prepare the data is rarely documented. The lab simplifies coding tasks, but the full analysis is complex, using custom code that ran on local resources within a custom environment. How can anyone reproduce those results, let alone use the techniques for other systems?

We will retrace the steps that would be needed to reproduce the results from two articles, one in physical oceanography and one in biogeochemistry. In the process, we will create an open-source computational component to a marine sciences lab, an interactive, online course that lowers the learning curve for using satellite data, and a recipe for transforming a traditional workflow into an open one. The recipe will be tested by issuing a challenge to reproduce the workflow, adapt the workflow for other systems, discover new science, and publish the results.

While the products created will be research specific, our methodology may be employed for any research topic in any discipline.

Scientific/Technical/Management

An Introduction to ScienceCore Carpentry

Researchers acquire knowledge, skills, and expertise over many years or even decades. The ‘instructions’ for their workflows often exist only in their minds and in a stockpile of scattered, uncommented scripts they have either written themselves or acquired from colleagues. Researchers have ‘hidden knowledge’, but the hiding is not done purposely or with malicious intent.

Consider a retired carpenter selling fine woodworking crafts at your local arts festival. You see a hand-carved birdhouse that you love. “That is amazing! I would love to make my own. How did you do that?” The carpenter says, “Well, I learned from my folks as a child, and I’ve been practicing ever since”. Sorry, no. The carpenter cannot teach you how to make that birdhouse.

“Wait...maybe you can’t teach me how to make *that* birdhouse, but what about a simpler one”? The carpenter agrees to teach basic woodworking at your community college. It is not an easy task. In order to successfully lead a class from beginner to birdhouse in three hours, the carpenter basically needs to design a ‘build a bird’ kit: instructions, prefabricated pieces, and an affordable and manageable subset of tools.

The researcher is that carpenter, and no, they cannot teach you how to build *that* birdhouse. But faculty researchers build ‘kits’ all the time, and they are called *undergraduate labs*. A lab translates fundamental science into a hands-on activity. Faculty design activities based on their research interests. The first phase of this project is **The Undergraduate Lab**. The labs include clear instructions on using simplified code to analyze and visualize a prepared dataset.

Your birdhouse building was a success, and you want to share it beyond your community. You want to take that kit to market! Uh-oh. The carpenter is the one who made the prefab pieces using some of their ‘hidden knowledge’. Now what?

The second phase of this project is **The Interactive Course**. It features all of the original material in The Undergraduate Lab, but it is adapted for use in a stand-alone class without an instructor. Additionally, it contains modules on what was done to find, get, clean, and process the original data in order to create the prefab datasets accompanying those Labs.

Now you are seriously invested in the birdhouse business. You want to make sure you developed a quality product, and you want that product to have high visibility and high impact. To do that, you host a competition: “Given the kit and some guidelines for making custom parts, show off your most amazing birdhouse at our next arts fair”.

The final phase of the project is **The OpenCore Article**. It demonstrates a workflow for publishing a scientific journal article using open-source science (OSS). We will take published research that originally inspired The Undergraduate Lab and rework the steps according to OSS principles. We will challenge others not only to reproduce the results, but to publish *new* results by modifying the workflow using datasets for a different time or location, or by choosing different analytical methods.

At the next arts fair, the carpenter walks by *your* booth, filled with custom creations. When the carpenter says, “Wow, those are amazing! How did they do that?” you will not only have an instruction manual, but you can point to the prominent attribution saying, ‘This work was made possible by The Carpenter’.

Objectives and Expected Significance

A specific objective with measurable results

Using existing research products as a starting point, we will create:

1. An open-source computational component to a marine sciences lab
2. An interactive, online course that lowers the learning curve for using satellite data
3. A recipe for transforming a traditional workflow into an open one

The transformed workflow will be tested by issuing a challenge to:

- reproduce the original workflow
- modify and adapt the workflow according to one’s own interests
- discover new science and publish the results

Our success will be measured by a report from faculty who incorporate the lab curriculum, information gathered from those who enroll in the online course, and progress towards publishable results by those modifying the workflow.

Achieving it in time

Faculty are expected to teach classes while maintaining high research productivity. A transition to open science involves the incredibly time-consuming task of carefully documenting both methods and code. If the objective is to make their workflow accessible to others, the most efficient way of doing so is as follows: let the researcher keep doing what they do best, and enlist help from experts in computation, training, and technical writing to collect, translate, and publish that workflow. When that workflow is published, other scientists—hopefully including the original researcher—can use it as a template for designing, documenting, and sharing the workflow for their next project.

A shift towards open science means a shift away from proprietary software. Seasoned researchers are extremely efficient at their programming language of choice. Squeezing in time for a few Python tutorials will not be sufficient to make the shift. We need to provide human resources—computational support—for porting proprietary code to

open-source equivalents before that faculty researcher points their next student to a stockpile of MATLAB scripts, saying: 'Here you go. Get me some plots by tomorrow!'

Keeping it relevant

A career choice in marine science is often inspired by nature. Students prefer to be in the field and are often highly resistant to the introduction of computational methods. Students must gain proficiency in computing to analyze datasets and communicate results; therefore, educators must incorporate data science into their lab curriculum.

The computational proficiency required to perform cutting-edge science has increased precipitously. Marine scientists must analyze large data sets, incorporate field work with satellite data, and share datasets in the cloud. Special curricula must be developed to help scientists to skill up quickly with minimal disruption to their current obligations.

The scientist and the student must be highly motivated by content that is directly relevant, concise, enjoyable, and has immediate impact on their current work. Creating such content is exceptionally challenging, especially from scratch. The challenge is often compounded by a lack of local expertise. Small institutions cannot justify the cost of hiring computational experts in absence of on-site advanced computing resources.

We will meet the first challenge in a fashion inspired by the Carpentries: do not attempt to create the content from scratch. Instead, seek out curated content with licensing that allows for using and redistributing content after adding subject specific material. We will overcome the second challenge by combining knowledge from a fieldwork focused marine sciences department with the expertise of a computational scientist who creates documentation and training materials for a high-performance computing (HPC) cluster.

Relevance and Impact

We will create open source training materials, giving equitable access to expertise in physical oceanography and biogeochemistry and lowering the learning curve for analyzing satellite data. We will demonstrate the development of an open science workflow by recreating the results of two publications: the first combines field data with MUR satellite data to understand the sea surface temperature conditions associated with a hurricane undergoing rapid intensification over the continental shelf[1], and the second demonstrates the use of locally calibrated satellite products to improve the satellite estimation of the partial pressure of carbon dioxide in coastal waters. The satellite data is from MODIS and VIIRS[2]. Data will be collected, processed, and analyzed using both core and discipline specific open-source data analysis and visualization libraries. While the products we create are research specific, our methodology may be employed for any research topic in any discipline.

Technical Approach and Methodology

Designing a Notebook

Past performance

Recognizing a need for students to learn data science, a marine sciences department resolved to develop a computational component to undergraduate labs. Evidence supported developing materials in Python, but faculty and teaching assistants (TAs) were proficient in MATLAB. Funding was secured for a consultant to prepare the first lab and to train TAs in the fundamentals of Python and Jupyter Notebook. The TAs quickly took over. They transformed lecture materials into markdown and translated coding tasks from MATLAB to Python. Remaining funds allowed for the consultant to assist with editing and troubleshooting and suggest alternatives for non-standard code.

General procedure

1. Faculty provide TAs with lecture notes and narrative, a conceptual outline of computational tasks, and MATLAB scripts used for completing those tasks.
2. TAs draft a Jupyter notebook, transforming narrative to markdown, and transforming the outline and original scripts into Python exercises.
3. The draft is passed to the consultant who edits the text for clarity and modifies coding exercises according to best practices when necessary.
4. The faculty reviews the draft for scientific accuracy and makes the final approval.

Design principles

Accessibility

To avoid any need for a massive overhaul late in the project, we will consult an accessibility coordinator early on. We know this will include closed captioning, video and figure captioning, palettes for color blindness, and writing styles for dyslexia. We will ask for advice on these and other requirements needed for 508 compliance.

Licensing

We will seek to use materials with Carpentries type licensing, i.e., CC BY, which allows for copying and redistributing the material in any format, and for remixing, transforming, and building upon the material for any purpose given an attribution and description of any modifications. We will share our work with the same licensing.

Follow community standards and best practices

Research software engineers develop tutorials on programming according to best practices and using community supported domain specific libraries. We will carefully search for such materials before creating our own, seeking CC BY and MIT licensing.

Avoid duplication, seek collaboration

Many data providers offer clear and comprehensive training materials for their products and the science behind them; we will not attempt to duplicate those materials. In cases where documentation is sparse or difficult for a new user to follow, we will invite collaboration by offering to share any materials developed while creating our modules.

Testing for UI/UX (User Interface / User Experience)

We will design the labs according to harsh lessons learned in creating other materials. The central philosophy is ‘make it easy for the user to do the right thing, and hard for them to do the wrong thing’. The harsh lesson is that you cannot anticipate successful UI/UX, you must rigorously test for it. We will actively invite (ask, coax, beg) user testing throughout the entire design process, continually modifying and improving both course and documentation based on user feedback and problems encountered.

The Undergraduate Lab

The Undergraduate Lab is designed to be a computational component to an in-person lab having teaching assistants and a professor. Science topics are those covered in physical and chemical oceanography, and computational topics include Python fundamentals (variables, types, operators), reading and manipulating data with pandas, mathematical operations and analysis with NumPy, and visualization tasks such as time series and contour plots with Matplotlib. Material is presented in a Jupyter notebook that can be completed within 2.5 hours.

The Interactive Course

Fundamental modules

For an online, interactive course that can be completed without instructor support, we start with the notebooks developed for the Lab, add researcher narrative and lecture material as video content, and add additional interactive exercises and quizzes. Additional video content will include interviews with the researcher describing their area of expertise, defining the problem to be solved, summarizing the analysis to be done, and explaining the significance of the results.

Modules on getting and preparing the data

The previous modules used a prepared dataset. These modules show how the dataset was prepared, including the following.

1. Choosing the data: Video interview with the scientist explaining why they chose the data product and where they got it from.
2. Getting the data:
 - a. Web interface: Show a short video on how to get that specific piece of data. Go to this website. Search for this keyword. Check these boxes or enter these numbers to limit the data. Download the data.

- b. For programmatic downloads not requiring credentials, explain the procedure and commands, and create an exercise for the download.
 - c. For programmatic downloads requiring cloud credentials or using cloud specific terminology, provide video and instruction to explain and simplify the procedure, and create an exercise for the download.
3. Preparing the data: we will describe what was needed to process the data, and we will provide the code and create an exercise for doing so in the notebook.

Modules on advanced topics

To be on the forefront of cutting-edge research, you need knowledge that is not necessarily hidden but often obscure: HPC, cloud computing, and web development. How so? For a cutting-edge research project, you might want to incorporate giant modeling outputs with real-time streaming satellite data and make the analysis easily accessible to stakeholders through a web browser.

We do not propose to develop a module for *that* project, but we will develop a few modules to demonstrate to researchers that these are not impossible tasks:

- Use an open-source, interactive mapping library (Leaflet), to explore field data.
- Apply for resources through NSF's ACCESS (Advanced Cyberinfrastructure Coordination Ecosystem: Services & Support) program, log in to a supercomputer, and run a Python workflow as a batch job.
- Use ACCESS cloud computing and storage to create a simple web application.

The OpenCore Article

Create an efficiently reproducible workflow

Following our own lesson plans developed for the Interactive Course, we will document the process of creating and sharing a workflow according to OSS principles. The process will include the following.

1. Prepare a GitHub repository with a README file. Make plans to commit changes and add detailed instructions to the README frequently throughout this process. Also, make a commitment to add comments and error checking for the code.
2. Start with a Lab notebook that explains the work and basic analysis used in a published research result. If several notebooks are needed, create a new notebook that combines the content.
3. Add Python code for programmatically downloading and processing all data needed for the full analysis.
4. Add and test any code that was in the original analysis but omitted from the labs.
5. Modify code to save images as files rather than displaying in a window. Convert code used for analysis and visualization into functions and create a library.
6. Replace the code blocks with library calls and confirm the results are the same.
7. Port the notebook to Python scripts that can be executed from the command line.
8. Make an inventory of all packages used in the workflow. Use this to create an environment file, including version numbers of both Python and packages.

9. Test the workflow within the environment and from the command line.

The process is complete when the workflow may be reproduced by cloning the repo and running the scripts from the command line according to the instructions in the README.

Test for usability and robustness

We will test the workflow internally by modifying the scripts to download satellite data from a different timeframe. We anticipate this will break the script, leading us to modify the training material, documentation, and code. When the new scripts and instructions are successful, we choose data from a different location and repeat the testing process.

During the testing process, we will continually build and improve documentation, commenting, and error checking for the workflow. When we are confident in the usability of our product, we will seek out researchers studying a similar topic in a different geographical location and invite them to try the analysis. We anticipate this will expose bugs in scripts and deficiencies in documentation, which we will work to correct.

Issue a challenge

When we feel our workflow is both easy to use and robust, we will issue a challenge for researchers to discover new science by adding custom modifications to type, time, and geographic location of data, and by using alternate statistical analysis and calibration parameters. Although we will issue a clear statement that we are unable to advise on the scientific validity of conclusions, we will welcome and address comments and criticism regarding the usability and robustness of the scripts and documentation.

Project Management and Risk Mitigation

PI will manage the project and coordinate efforts to ensure timely completion of milestones and deliverables. Project team has access and approval to share, use, and modify a draft of the Undergraduate Lab and any MATLAB scripts used in the publications. PI will be responsible for course design, computer programming, recruiting researchers and students to test materials, and providing computational support to those who agree to test. Co-Is will advise on procedures and methods for interacting with satellite data and review the final products for scientific accuracy. Co-Is will mentor a graduate student who will not only use and test the workflow but contribute to it by documenting their progress and learning process.

We have proposed to create training materials and share 'Workflow as Code' for two publications by the end of the second project year. Completing these ahead of schedule would allow us time to create additional modules or to expand support for user testing. Underestimating complexity of tasks may result in not having sufficient time to deliver both workflows; however, this project is designed to deliver value on a per-task level continuously throughout the project. The workflow for [1] will be delivered in its entirety. Workflow [2] has higher complexity and therefore has higher uncertainty when estimating effort required for full completion, but each step taken in the process will

result in a viable product, such as course modules for specific satellite data and open-source translations of MATLAB functions.

Mitigating the following risks may necessitate modifying or reducing project scope:

- Researchers may have forgotten specific details or misplaced scripts used in the original publications. Project team will fill in missing details, but that will add to the time required to complete the related tasks.
- We may encounter difficulties securing an intern to assist with time-consuming tasks such as video editing and captioning visual content. The project team would need to complete these tasks instead of focusing their efforts on more advanced content.
- Failure to enlist sufficient participation from a diverse pool of students and researchers will prevent comprehensive user testing and limit progress towards publishable results. Project team will perform testing and pursue publications using modified workflows, but true user testing must be performed by those unfamiliar with the subject matter and specific methods.

Work Plan, Milestones, and Deliverables

Tasks required to complete milestones and deliverables are largely decoupled, but they will be listed in approximate order of expected completion.

Year 1

Overall design and planning

- Sketch out the overall design of the course. Schedule a consultation to review the sketch with University Information Technology accessibility services and with University Libraries' support center for licensing, open education, open science, and critical approaches to data and technology.
- Review and incorporate new OpenCore content into existing and future labs.
- Initial course development will be in Jupyter Books. Learn the Open edX platform to add videos and quizzes more effectively and enable the gathering of statistics.
- Begin the planning process with Communications Department to sponsor an undergraduate internship in Year 2, for Digital Film and TV or related majors.

Milestones toward Undergraduate Lab

- Review existing Lab notebooks and modify as needed to conform to OpenCore recommendations and best programming practices. Make the labs available on TOPS GitHub.

Inclusion – Undergraduate Lab

- Invite users to try the Lab, providing instructions for creating GitHub issues to track and address comments, corrections, or feature requests.

Deliverable – Undergraduate Lab

- Labs are available to anyone with internet access using Binder. Instructions are provided for running locally with Anaconda Navigator.

Milestones toward Interactive Course materials

- Populate initial GitHub repo for Course materials and another for Article [1] with READMEs and general instructions.
- Collect MATLAB scripts and information on the data processing needed to replicate the publications. Start drafting the Python code.
- Create draft notebooks with instructions and code for collecting the satellite data. Take screen captures and record video meetings with screen sharing. Start storyboarding and scripting narrative to plan for the video segments.
- Create a notebook that uses Leaflet as first-order error checking after downloading and processing field data.
- Draft advanced modules by mentoring a graduate student to apply for ACCESS resources, run Python scripts as batch jobs, and host a Flask (Python+Leaflet) web application using cloud computing and storage resources.

Deliverable – OpenCore Article [1]

- Workflow for [1] in sufficient form that it may be efficiently replicated and modified by Co-I's graduate student, with intent on pursuing publishable results.

Year 2

Challenge – OpenCore Article [1]

- Issue a challenge for external users to reproduce Article [1] and make discovery.

Milestones toward Interactive Course materials

- Find or create images, figures, and diagrams. Take photography and video. Edit and finalize video content from storyboards and related material. Incorporate additional material as needed for accessibility, including captioning and audio explanations for figures and video.
- Populate Open edX with content from Jupyter Books. Add quizzes and video.
- Test course materials on multiple platforms.

Inclusion – Interactive Course materials

- Invite users to try the Course, providing instructions for creating GitHub issues to track and address comments, corrections, or feature requests.

Deliverable – Interactive Course materials

- Final version of the Interactive Course is on Open edX.

Deliverable – OpenCore Article [2]

- Workflow for [2] in sufficient form that it may be efficiently replicated and modified by Co-I's graduate student, with intent on pursuing publishable results.

Challenge – OpenCore Article [2]

- Issue a challenge for external users to reproduce Article [2] and make discovery.

Deliverable – Metrics

- Compile a report summarizing successes and failures in eliciting participation and providing support, feedback gathered from user testing, progress towards results and publications, and suggestions on how our methods could be improved.

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION

Senior Personnel

PI

The PI will be responsible for the overall coordination of the project and the coordination of the project personnel. PI will be responsible for course design, writing code according to best practices, recruiting researchers and students to test materials, and providing computational support to those who agree to test. PI will be responsible for the design and implementation of translating an interactive, multi-step processed workflow into an automated workflow that can be run from the command line on various architectures.

Co-I#1

Co-I will provide subject matter expertise (SME) in physical oceanography and will contribute to the development of case scenarios, identify best-fit NASA products, and review all content for scientific accuracy. Co-I's focus will be on developing and reviewing material related to ocean physics.

Co-I#2

Co-I will provide SME in marine biogeochemistry and will similarly develop case scenarios, identify best-fit NASA products, and review all content for scientific accuracy. Co-I's focus will be on developing and reviewing material related to marine biogeochemistry and ecology system dynamics.

Other Personnel

Graduate Student

A graduate student will work directly on this project and contribute to the development of educational modules related to their dissertation research. This will involve documenting the process of collecting and analyzing NASA satellite data and data products as well as serving as a developer and 'tester' of training and educational material that are generated by the project.

Travel

Domestic Travel

Travel funds are requested for the PI to attend the yearly NASA TOPS organizational meeting. Funds are requested for Co-Is or graduate student to disseminate research results at domestic meetings such as AGU Ocean Science Meeting.

Other Direct Costs

Materials and Supplies

Cost of a computer or the graduate student in Year 1, and a yearly cost for MATLAB licenses and data storage devices are budgeted for costs associated with code and course content development.

Publication Costs

Requested in Year 2 for one open access publication of research results and the preparation of presentations and posters for research dissemination.

Other

GRA tuition is requested for one calendar year of the project.

References

- [1] Dzwonkowski, B. S. Fourier, G. Lockridge, Z. Liu, J. Coogan, and K. Park (2022) Hurricane Sally (2020) shifts the ocean thermal structure across the inner core during rapid intensification over the shelf, *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 52(11), 2841-2852
- [2] Le, C., Y. Gao, W-J. Cai, J. Lehrter, Y. Bai, and Z-P. Jiang (2019), Estimating summer sea surface pCO₂ on a river-dominated continental shelf using a satellite-based semi-mechanistic model. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 225, 115-126.

Open-Source Science Development Plan

Early and Often

Open-source science is a commitment to the open sharing ...as early as possible in the scientific process.

GitHub repos will be prepared before work begins. Instructions, including short videos, teaching the basics of GitHub, including fork and pull requests, will be created to train project members and students. Later, those materials will be incorporated into the Interactive Course. A part of the project is porting MATLAB to Python. We would populate a repo with MATLAB scripts before the translation process begins, along with creating a README file that lists repo contents and outlines translation methodology and testing criterion. We will contact faculty and students who have lamented being stuck with legacy MATLAB and invite them to look, ask questions, make comments, and find bugs. We will use that type of mindset and methodology throughout the project.

Transparent, Accessible, and Inclusive

*OPEN (TRANSPARENT) SCIENCE - scientific process and results should be **visible**, **accessible**, and **understandable**.*

Sharing in GitHub will make results **visible**, but help is needed to make it **accessible** and **understandable**. Knowing that use of GitHub is *non-trivial* for newcomers allows us create 'help' that is understandable. Knowing that git/GitHub is *not user friendly* for some compute environments, e.g., Windows, allows us to help make things accessible.

*OPEN (ACCESSIBLE) SCIENCE – data, tools, software, documentation, and publications should be **accessible** to all*

Putting code in GitHub and making data and results freely available via the cloud makes them **available** but not necessarily **accessible**. We often see instructions starting with 'fork the repository' or 'modify the permissions on the access key'. This causes some experienced researchers to pause and some newcomers to stop reading entirely. In our experience, just asking folks to 'open an issue' can be intimidating. A 30 second video could easily clear things up. We will create documentation that is accessible to all.

*OPEN (INCLUSIVE) SCIENCE – process and participants should **welcome participation** by and **collaboration** with diverse people and organizations*

Simply making that 30 second video will not help if people don't know where to look for it. Research facilities may set aside funds for underserved institutions to 'apply' for resources, but that alone is insufficient. First, they need to know the opportunity exists, why it might benefit them, and how to apply. Second, to successfully and sustainably onboard newcomers, there generally needs to be a *local* resource to provide support, i.e., dedicated staff already working at the underserved institution. This is a chicken and egg problem. The solution is 1) active, personalized outreach and 2) partial FTE for expert staff to provide support until the institution builds their own community of

practice. Specifically, a TOPS award could provide means for an experienced project team to identify department heads at nearby HBCUs and community colleges then send a specific, personal email to those leaders offering a concrete activity with dedicated assistance. Instead of advertising a blanket opportunity that hopefully reaches the intended audience, send an email to a faculty teaching a relevant topic that says:

Dear Professor,

My team is creating a Python course for marine sciences. I was wondering if you would possibly be willing to invite your students or colleagues to try it out. We really need user feedback to improve the course, and we can offer to provide office hours or respond to questions via email.

*Thank you for your consideration,
Project Lead*

Our team will actively strive to engage a wide audience. Success will be measured in participation, feedback, and progress towards publications.

Reproducible

*OPEN (REPRODUCIBLE) SCIENCE – scientific process and **results should be** open such that they are **reproducible** by members of the community*

There is an underlying problem with making code visible and accessible: a researcher uses research grade code. Sharing that code to a wide audience of budding researchers may be counter to our goals. Open science is transparent, reproducible, and accessible. The typical research grade code is often scant in commenting, devoid of error checking, and is almost guaranteed to give different results depending on who runs it. The tried and tested scripts are often in proprietary software (e.g., MATLAB), because the open-source scripts tend to break with each version release.

Our team has supported users with varying expertise, operating systems, instruction set architecture, number of parallel threads, compiler versions and flags...we've seen it all. Since we are largely working with Python scripts, using an environment file with version numbers then testing on different operating systems and comparing the results will expose the vast majority of errors. (Determining whether 'different answer' means 'wrong' is also a topic worth serious discussion.) Inviting as many people as possible to try the notebooks or run the workflow will expose more problems. The process of solving them will lead to improved documentation and more robust error checking.

Licensing

We plan to share the course materials under the CC BY license and the code under the MIT License. We will consult the latest OpenCore materials and modify our plan should they suggest something different.